

Alkali Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of β -Alaninates with Some Oxygen and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Mixed ligand complexes of the general formula ML_nHL' have been synthesised where $M = Li, Na, K, Rb,$ and Cs ; $HL = \beta$ -alanine and $HL' = 8$ -hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetone. The value of n is usually one, but in some cases, specially with Rb and Cs, the value is either 2 or 3, suggesting coordination number six or greater than six.

These complexes have been found to be stabler than the corresponding glycine compounds ; and pK has been found not to be the dominant factor in the formation of these mixed ligand complexes.

WORKING on the same line as that of alkali metal glycinate (previous paper), 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, isonitrosoacetophenone, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetone formed a number of stable mixed ligand complexes with alkali metal salts of β -alanine. Analytical data showed that one molecule of potassium, rubidium and caesium salts of β -alanine combined with two or three molecules of 8-hydroxyquinoline, *o*-nitrophenol and acetylacetone, suggesting a coordination number greater than six in some cases.

Results and Discussions

It has been found that the second ligands which have lower pK values than β -alanine, also formed adducts with β -alanine salts (just like glycinate) and do not replace the β -alanine from their salts. The mixed ligand complexes of glycine salts, have been found to be less stable than β -alanine complexes.

β -Alanine is insoluble in absolute ethanol but its alkali metal salts are soluble on heating in ethanol solvent showing some covalent character.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Transition ($t^\circ C$) or decomp. ($d^\circ C$) temperatures.	Found			Calcd		
			C	H	M	C	H	M
LiAln.8HQ	White	158 t	60.53	5.97		60.00	5.42	
NaAln.8HQ	White	138 t	56.42	5.03	8.15	56.52	5.07	8.98
KAln.(8HQ) ₂	White	145-50 d	60.95	4.66	9.10	60.43	4.80	9.35
RbAln.(8HQ) ₂	White	121 t	58.86	4.29	13.25	59.21	4.44	13.98
CsAln.(8HQ) ₂	White	114 t	55.02	4.08	19.45	54.96	4.12	20.15
LiAln.1N2N	Brown	185 t	58.80	5.00		58.20	4.85	
NaAln.1N2N	Brown	160 t	54.36	4.34	7.95	54.93	4.57	8.09
KAln.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	135 t	59.02	4.07	7.98	58.35	4.22	8.24
RbAln.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	132 t	53.53	3.85	16.40	53.17	3.85	16.17
CsAln.(1N2N) ₂	Brown	186 d	48.46	3.61	22.85	48.51	3.50	23.32
NaAln.INAP	Pale yellow	121 t	50.60	4.60	8.55	50.96	4.51	8.84
KAln.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	113 t	53.60	5.15	8.88	53.90	4.95	9.17
RbAln.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	110 t	48.28	3.86	17.70	48.61	3.83	18.04
CsAln.(INAP) ₂	Pale yellow	105 t	43.59	3.82	24.85	44.18	3.48	25.48
LiAln.ONP	Yellow	220 d	45.95	5.02		46.53	4.70	
NaAln.ONP	Yellow	160 t	43.37	4.39	8.70	43.20	4.40	9.20
KAln.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	116 t	47.88	4.40	9.98	48.52	4.28	10.45
RbAln.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	185 t	42.02	3.67	14.20	42.71	3.55	14.40
CsAln.(ONP) ₂	Yellow	175 t	39.64	3.05	19.90	39.56	3.29	20.72
LiAln.acac	White	220 t	48.98	7.05		49.23	7.07	
NaAln.acac	Pale yellow	70 t	45.64	6.46	9.98	54.49	6.63	10.90
KAln.(acac) ₂	White	185 d	46.50	6.44	10.99	46.29	6.51	11.95
RbAln.(acac) ₂	White	183 d	45.68	5.82	17.50	45.66	6.34	17.97
CsAln.(acac) ₂	White	194 d	41.30	6.11	25.50	41.53	5.77	25.38

Aln= β -Alanine ; 8HQ=8-Hydroxyquinoline ; 1N2N=1-Nitroso-2-naphthol ; INAP=isonitrosoacetophenone ; acac=acetylacetone ; and ONP=*o*-nitrophenol.

The method of preparation of these adducts is same as that of metal-salts of glycinate (previous paper).

In our previous work we observed that in the mixed ligand complexes of the general formula $ML_n.nHL'$, n had always been one. With β -alanine alkali salt adducts, the value of n is one only for lithium and sodium, whereas in potassium, rubidium and caesium adducts, the number of second ligand is more than one, usually two (K) and three (Rb and Cs).

Analytical results, some physical properties and selected i.r. bands are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Infrared spectra: Similar to the metal-glycinate mixed ligand complexes, the spectra of the β -alanine mixed ligand complexes also show number of unexpected

features :

- The O-H stretching frequency of the second ligands 8HQ, 1N2N and INAP is absent in the complexes.
- There are no N-H peaks above 3000 cm^{-1} in the complexes of 8HQ, 1N2N, & INAP. In ONP and acac complexes, there appear a weak and broad absorption peak centred around 3100 cm^{-1} and only in $RbAln.(ONP)_3$ and $CsAln.(ONP)_3$ a second peak of medium intensity is at 3180 cm^{-1} .
- A new broad band of medium intensity (better resolved than the corresponding glycinate complexes) with submaxima at 2600 cm^{-1} and 2710 cm^{-1} are seen in most of the complexes, which are absent in the two ingredients. On the assumptions and arguments put forward in the case of the mixed ligand complexes of glycinate, these two peaks between $2600\text{--}2710\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in β -alanine complexes have been assigned to N..H..O. bonding.

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (IN CM^{-1}).

Compound	3500—3000	2800 — 2300	2300 — 1800	1700 — 1500
8-Hydroxyquinoline (8HQ)	3440			1580 (C=N)
LiAln.8HQ		2710 2520	2150br	1630 1610 1575 1550sh 1500
NaAln.8HQ		2600br		1630 1610 1575 1540 1500
KAln.(8HQ) ₂		2600 2500br	1800	1640 1615 1580 1560 1530
RbAln.(8HQ) ₃			2200br	1640 1620 1570 1550
CsAln.(8HQ) ₃	3150br	2710 2540br	2150	1650 1620 1580sh 1525 1500 1550
1-Nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N)	3300br 3055			1640 (N=O)
LiAln.1N2N		2710 2600	2195	1650 1635 1570 1550 1500
NaAln.1N2N		2400	2220	1650 1630 1580 1510 1500 1570
KAln.(1N2N) ₂		2620	2190s	1650 1625 1580 1560 1510
RbAln.(1N2N) ₂		2710 2620	2193	1640 1630 1580 1563 1500 1600
CsAln.(1N2N) ₂	3100br	2710 2620	2200s	1630 1610 1590 1580 1500
Isonitrosoacetophenone (INAP)	3260			1680 (C=O)
NaAln.INAP		2680	2220	1680sh 1615 1600 1560
KAln.(INAP) ₂		2710 2620	2200m 1900	1670 1620 1590 1540
RbAln.(INAP) ₃		2710 2600	2180m 1900	1665 1620 1580 1550
CsAln.(INAP) ₃		2720 2610	2180m 1890	1680sh 1660 1620 1585 1560
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol (ONP)	3218			1615 (N=O)
LiAln.ONP	3100br	2710 2600	2180s	1650sh 1630sh 1610 1550 1520
NaAln.ONP		2700 2620	2180s	1650sh 1652sh 1615 1560 1520
KAln.(ONP) ₂	3100br	2610 2500	2200s	1600sh 1630 1580 1500 1540
RbAln.(ONP) ₃	3180 3100br	2710 2620	2180s	1650sh 1620 1580 1530sh
CsAln.(ONP) ₃	3180 3100br	2710—2620br	2190s	1650—1620br 1580 1510
Acetylacetone (acac)				1735 1625br 1720
LiAln.acac	3100br		2190s	1660sh 1630 1560 1500
NaAln.acac		2600w	2180m	1660sh 1620 1570 1530sh 1500
KAln.(acac) ₂	3100br	2620	2200s	1660sh 1630 1570 1500
RbAln.(acac) ₃	3100br	2600w	2190m	1660sh 1620 1560 1510sh 1500
CsAln.(acac) ₃	3100br	2600w	2190m	1660sh 1630 1570 1500

(d) Another new medium to strong band around 2200 cm^{-1} (in 3 or 4 cases around 1900 cm^{-1}) is seen in all the complexes which again have been assigned to strong hydrogen bonding O . H . O.

All the second ligands being potential chelates, the bands corresponding to the site of attachment in these ligands similar to glycinate have been found to be metal sensitive.

The 8HQ complexes of Li and Na are similar but different from K, Rb & Cs, which again in turn show similarity among themselves. The C=N band of 8HQ at 1580 cm^{-1} shifts to 1575 cm^{-1} in Li & Na and show two peaks '1580, 1560,' '1580, 1550,' and '1580, 1550' cm^{-1} for the corresponding K, Rb and Cs complexes respectively.

The spectra of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol complexes are similar and the N=O ligand band at 1640 cm^{-1} shows a gradual shift from 1635 cm^{-1} for Li to 1610 cm^{-1} for Cs.

The Na, K & Rb complexes with isonitrosoacetophenone again are similar and show the C=O peak of

ligand (1680 cm^{-1}) at $1680, 1670$ & 1665 cm^{-1} respectively; whereas Cs is different from the rest and show two peaks, one at 1680 cm^{-1} and the other at 1660 cm^{-1} .

The *o*-nitrophenol adducts like the glycinate may not be complexes but acid salts. The well resolved medium peaks at about 2600 cm^{-1} and strong absorption around 2200 cm^{-1} , suggest very strong hydrogen bonding. Moreover two distinct peaks are observed above 3000 cm^{-1} in all the complexes. Further the N=O band at 1615 cm^{-1} do not show any regular change from Li to Cs complexes.

The broad band around 1570 cm^{-1} assigned to C=O in acetylacetone do not give any information as to the coordination site of acac in the β -alanine complexes. The three bands around, 1660 cm^{-1} , 630 cm^{-1} and 1560 cm^{-1} in the complexes can not be assigned to any particular frequency. The N-H stretching region around 3100 cm^{-1} show weak, broad peaks which are poorly resolved; N . H . O assigned to 2600 cm^{-1} bands are also weak. But 2200 cm^{-1} bands are of medium to strong intensity suggesting strong hydrogen bonding.